

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Using Learning Assistants to Engage Students in Case/Problem-based Learning in a Physiology Course

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Sample Discussion Worksheet

Note: The questions include a breakdown of which Bloom's Taxonomy level was integrated in the development of the question. Additionally, all figures utilized in the worksheet have been removed due to copyright laws.

PhySci 111B Spring 2022, Week 2 Hypothalamic Regulation of Homeostasis and the HPA axis

1. a) What is pulsatile activity, and why is it significant in the HPG axis?

Answer: Pulsatile activity implicates time-dependent recurrences. In the HPG axis, hormone levels rise in pulsatile fashion.

Bloom's Taxonomy Level: Remember

b) Portal GnRH concentrations were shown to spike in a patient at 12:00, 14:30, 17:00, and 19:30. Upon drawing blood from the arm at 17:00, what hormone would you expect to see in relatively high levels (in regard to HPG axis)?

Answer: FSH is expected since it is characterized by the slow pulsation of GnRH (less than 1 pulse every 2 to 3 hours).

Bloom's Taxonomy Level: Understand

2. Reference the image to the right (image removed due to copyright laws). Suppose the arcuate nucleus of the hypothalamus is damaged and its neurons are nonfunctional. Describe what you would expect to see in HPG axis hormone levels when estrogen levels are high.

Answer: We would expect to see increased kisspeptin from the AVPV, and more GnRH would be released.

Bloom's Taxonomy Level: Apply

3. Breast cancer cells in postmenopausal women express estrogen receptors, and when bound, the cells multiply rapidly. What might be an effective treatment method to prevent the proliferation of the tumor cells?

Answer: Implementation of estrogen-receptor antagonist (blocks the estrogen receptor before circulating E2 can bind)! This prevents gene transcription and therefore multiplication of these cancer cells. Tamoxifen is a common drug that does similar functions to this.

Aromatase inhibitors can also work to prevent conversion of androgens into estrogens.

However, this *might* have a negative effect on other things that estrogen regulates like bone density, temperature, etc.

Guiding point for Learning Assistants : Tamoxifen - acts as an estrogen receptor agonist (mimics estrogen's effects) on some tissues, but can act as an estrogen receptor antagonist (inhibit estrogen's effects) on other tissues. You can guide the students by having them think about what estrogen does to these cancer cells.

Bloom's Taxonomy Level: Analyze

4. Compare and contrast glucocorticoid and mineralocorticoid receptors to adrenergic receptors. What are the advantages of each type of receptor?

Answer: Aldosterone and cortisol signal target cells/tissues through nuclear receptors. Type 1 mineralocorticoid receptors (MRs) have a high affinity for circulating cortisol and aldosterone. Since they have a high affinity, they are very sensitive to cortisol and aldosterone therefore they are expressed only in the hippocampus, central nucleus of the

amygdala, and the lateral and medial septum.

Type 2 glucocorticoid receptors (GRs) have a low affinity for cortisol and will be activated when circulating cortisol levels are particularly high. These receptors are expressed ubiquitously in the tissues of the body because they require a lot of cortisol to be active. This is advantageous because you wouldn't want to engage the stress response quickly throughout the body at the slightest increase of cortisol secretion as cortisol is also regulated by circadian rhythms and not only the stress response. GRs in the paraventricular nucleus (PVN) and anterior pituitary will mediate negative feedback of the HPA axis when high cortisol levels are detected. Both receptor types have a function in slowing transcriptional changes.

Adrenergic receptors are a type of GPCR. Alpha and beta-adrenergic receptors are sensitive to norepinephrine and epinephrine in different ways. Alpha1 and alpha2 adrenergic receptors have a greater sensitivity to NE, which is released at lower quantities from the chromaffin cells during the stress response. B2 almost exclusively binds E, which is released at high levels from the adrenal medulla during activation of the HPA axis.

Each receptor has a different physiological effect depending on the neurotransmitter it binds. This is advantageous because it allows for a tissue-specific response to a singular stimulus quickly. For example, E will bind B2, which will activate the adenylyl-cyclase GPCR. This will cause heart muscle contraction, smooth muscle relaxation, and glycogenolysis. When NE binds to alpha1, the phospholipase C GPCR will cause smooth muscle contraction. This will mediate tissue specific responses and will help regulate the desired effects during the stress response.

Bloom's Taxonomy Level: Apply

5. You are shadowing an endocrinologist for the day, and you are informed that a patient has a mutation in the gene that encodes for the enzyme **17 α -hydroxylase**. Answer the following questions about the patient using lecture material and the chart provided.

a. Mark on the steroid synthesis chart where this mutation is (chart removed due to copyright laws). As a consequence, which steroid hormone will build up in excess?

Answer: Students will mark this mutation on the chart. The steroid hormones pregnenolone and progesterone will build up in excess. If 3beta-Hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase (3beta-HSD) still works, pregnenolone can be converted to progesterone.

Bloom's Taxonomy Level: Apply

b. Which steroid hormones will be reduced in their production due to this mutation?

Answer: 17alpha-hydroxypregnenolone and 17 alpha-hydroxyprogesterone

Bloom's Taxonomy Level: Apply

c. Would you expect a patient with this mutation to exhibit the same side effect profile of Congenital Adrenal Hyperplasia? Why or why not?

Answer: No, I would not suspect that this patient would exhibit the same side effect profile because so long as the 21-hydroxylase and 11beta-hydroxylase enzymes are functional, an excess amount of progesterone will still be converted to deoxycorticosterone and subsequently corticosterone. There will be a reduction in cortisol however, so this may cause some side effects in the patient similar to the disease but not entirely. Aldosterone will be able to be produced regardless, so that aspect of the side effect profile of Congenital Adrenal Hyperplasia will not be exhibited.

Bloom's Taxonomy Level: Evaluate

Pre-Course Survey Instrument

1. With respect to your learning broadly and in THIS course, please rate the following statements (1= strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= neither agree or disagree, 4= agree, 5 = strongly agree).

Note: These questions are targeted at assessing student metacognition.

- a) I will be a good judge of how well I will understand something in 111B.
- b) I will decipher what kind of information is most important to learn in 111B.
- c) I know what the professors expect me to learn in 111B.
- d) I can motivate myself to learn when I need to.
- e) I learn best when I know something about the topic.
- f) I use my intellectual strengths to compensate for my weaknesses.
- g) I try to use strategies that have worked in the past.
- h) I find myself using helpful learning strategies automatically.
- i) I ask myself periodically if I am meeting my goals.
- j) I ask myself questions about how well I am doing while learning something new.
- k) I ask myself questions about the material before I begin studying.
- l) I set specific goals before I begin studying.
- m) I think of several ways to solve a problem and choose the best one.
- n) I ask myself how well I accomplish my goals once I'm finished.
- o) I ask myself if I have considered all options after I solve a problem.

2. With respect to how you view yourself in relation to the major and field , please rate the following statements (1= strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= neither agree or disagree, 4= agree, 5 = strongly agree).

Note: These questions are targeted at assessing a student's disciplinary identity.

- a) I am interested in learning more about Physiology.
- b) I enjoy learning Physiology.
- c) Topics in Physiology excite my curiosity.
- d) I see myself as a Physiology person.
- e) My family sees me as a Physiology person.
- f) My friends/classmates see me as a Physiology person.
- g) My instructors/teachers see me as a Physiology person.
- h) I am confident that I can understand the information covered in PhySci 111B.
- i) I can do well on exams in PhySci 111B.
- j) I understand concepts I have studied in Physiology.
- k) Others ask me for help in Physiology.
- l) I can overcome setbacks in Physiology.

3. Have you taken a course that was supported by learning assistants? (If yes, proceed to the next question. If no, move on to the next section).

- Yes
- No

4. If you answered yes to the question above, please indicate how many courses.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5+

5. If you have taken a course with LAs, please indicate which course(s) they were present in. **(open-ended question)**

6. If you have taken courses with LAs, what are the benefits and drawbacks of having learning assistant support in a classroom? **(open-ended question)**

7. To what extent did you find LAs helpful with the following within courses you have taken in the past? (1= Very Unhelpful, 2= Unhelpful, 3= Neither Helpful or Unhelpful, 4= Helpful, 5= Very Helpful).

- a) The LA helped me solidify my understanding of the material.
- b) The LA helped me gain confidence in my abilities to succeed in the course.
- c) The LA helped me build a sense of community and belonging within my major.
- d) The LA helped me develop more efficient studying strategies.
- e) The LA helped me become a more motivated student.

8. Have you taken any courses that have used problem-based learning (PBL)?

- Yes
- No
- Unsure
- I don't know what problem-based learning is.

9. If you have taken courses with problem-based learning (PBL), please indicate which courses they were in (note: if you have not taken any courses where PBL was prevalent, please skip ahead to the next section).

10. If you have taken courses with problem-based learning, what are the benefits and drawbacks of using problem-based learning in a classroom?

11. To what extent do you agree with the following statements about problem-based learning (PBL)? (1= strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= neither agree or disagree, 4= agree, 5 = strongly agree)

- a) PBL allows me to better assess my knowledge gaps while studying.
- b) PBL allows me to develop critical thinking skills.
- c) When I am able to answer questions correctly during PBL, I feel more confident in my ability to do well in the course.
- d) PBL allows me to actively understand the material I am studying.
- e) PBL allows me to find a sense of belonging and community with people from my major.

12. Are the upper division Anatomy and Physiology courses (i.e. 107, 111A, & 111B) your first exposure to Anatomy and Physiology at UCLA?

- Yes
- No
- Unsure

13. If your answer to the above question is no, please list the name of the Anatomy and/or Physiology course you took at UCLA. If your answer to the above question is yes, please type in N/A. **(open-ended question)**

14. Did you have any exposure to Anatomy and/or Physiology in high school?

- Yes
- No

15. If your answer to the above question is yes, please select how many courses. If your answer to the question above is no, please select N/A.

- 1
- 2
- 3+
- N/A

16. Are you a first-generation college student (i.e. the first in your family to attend a US 4- year institution)?

- Yes
- No

17. Are you the first in your family pursuing a career in STEM?

- Yes
- No

18. Do your parents/guardians/primary caregivers hold occupations in STEM?

- Yes
- No

19. What do you plan to do after graduation?

- Medical School (MD, DO)
- Dental School (DMD, DDS)
- Graduate School (Masters, PhD)
- PT School (DPT)
- Research/lab tech
- K-12 teaching

Post-Course Survey Instrument

1. With respect to your learning after completing THIS course (PhySci 111B), please rate the following statements (1= strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= neither agree or disagree, 4= agree, 5 = strongly agree).

Note: These questions are targeted at assessing student metacognition.

- a) I will be a good judge of how well I will understand something in 111B.
- b) I will decipher what kind of information is most important to learn in 111B.
- c) I know what the professors expect me to learn in 111B.
- d) I can motivate myself to learn when I need to.
- e) I learn best when I know something about the topic.
- f) I use my intellectual strengths to compensate for my weaknesses.
- g) I try to use strategies that have worked in the past.
- h) I find myself using helpful learning strategies automatically.
- i) I ask myself periodically if I am meeting my goals.
- j) I ask myself questions about how well I am doing while learning something new.
- k) I ask myself questions about the material before I begin studying.
- l) I set specific goals before I begin studying.
- m) I think of several ways to solve a problem and choose the best one.
- n) I ask myself how well I accomplish my goals once I'm finished.
- o) I ask myself if I have considered all options after I solve a problem.

2. With respect to how you view yourself in relation to the major and field after having taken PhySci 111B, please rate the following statements (1= strongly disagree , 5 = strongly agree).

Note: These questions are targeted at assessing a student's disciplinary identity.

- a) I am interested in learning more about Physiology.
- b) I enjoy learning Physiology.
- c) Topics in Physiology excite my curiosity.
- d) I see myself as a Physiology person.
- e) My family sees me as a Physiology person.
- f) My friends/classmates see me as a Physiology person.
- g) My instructors/teachers see me as a Physiology person.
- h) I am confident that I can understand the information covered in PhySci 111B.
- i) I can do well on exams in PhySci 111B.
- j) I understand concepts I have studied in Physiology.
- k) Others ask me for help in Physiology.
- l) I can overcome setbacks in Physiology.

3. Did you find learning assistants integral to your learning in PS 111B?

Yes

No

4. Please elaborate on your response to the prior question. Note: Please do not write N/A as a response. **(open-ended question)**

5. In your opinion, what are the benefits and drawbacks of having learning assistant support in PhySci 111B? **(open-ended question)**

6. To what extent did you find LAs helpful with the following within PhySci 111B? (1= Very Unhelpful, 2= Unhelpful, 3= Neither Helpful or Unhelpful, 4= Helpful, 5= Very Helpful).

- a) The LA helped me solidify my understanding of the material.
- b) The LA helped me gain confidence in my abilities to succeed in the course.
- c) The LA helped me build a sense of community and belonging within my major.
- d) The LA helped me develop more efficient studying strategies.
- e) The LA helped me become a more motivated student.

7. Did you find the problem-based learning discussion worksheets integral to your learning in PS 111B?

- Yes
- No

8. Please elaborate on your response to the prior question. Note: Please do not write N/A as a response. **(open-ended question)**

9. In your opinion, what are the benefits and drawbacks of using problem-based learning during discussions in PS 111B? **(open-ended question)**

10. To what extent do you agree with the following statements about problem-based learning (PBL) within PS 111B? (1= strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= neither agree or disagree, 4= agree, 5 = strongly agree)

- a) PBL allowed me to better assess my knowledge gaps while studying.
- b) PBL allowed me to develop critical thinking skills.
- c) When I was able to answer questions correctly during PBL, I felt more confident in my ability to do well in the course.
- d) PBL allowed me to actively understand the material I was studying.
- e) PBL allowed me to find a sense of belonging and community with people from my major.
- f) PBL allowed me to showcase my knowledge to my peers and TAs.

11. After completing the upper division Anatomy and Physiology courses (i.e. 107, 111A, & 111B) with learning assistants (LAs) and problem-based learning (PBL) worksheets, to what extent do you agree with the following statements? (1= strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= neither agree or disagree, 4= agree, 5 = strongly agree).

- a) Utilizing PBL worksheets helped me succeed on exams.
- b) PBL discussion worksheets helped me master fundamental concepts in Anatomy and Physiology.
- c) I feel more confident in communicating Anatomy and Physiology with my peers because of PBL.
- d) I am able to simplify difficult concepts into simpler ideas because of the skills I have acquired from PBL discussion worksheets.
- e) PBL discussion worksheets made discussion worksheets more meaningful for my learning.

- f) PBL discussion worksheets made me more conscious of topics I was struggling with.
- g) Having LAs within the discussion sections helped me feel more welcomed within the major.
- h) Collaborating with the LAs made me more conscious of the topics I was struggling with.
- i) The LAs helped me simplify more complex ideas into simpler parts.
- j) I feel more confident in communicating Anatomy and Physiology with my peers because of my LAs.
- k) Having LAs be present made me feel like I can succeed within this field.
- l) I am motivated to become an LA for this course because of the LAs I have had.

12. After completing the upper division Anatomy and Physiology courses (i.e. 107, 111A, & 111B), would you recommend this major to incoming students at UCLA?

- Yes
- No
- Unsure

Post-Course Survey Open-Ended Question Responses on Learning Assistants

Question: Did you find Learning Assistants integral to your learning in PS 111B?

- Our TA helped fill in gaps of knowledge and gave advice for exams.
- My learning assistant was great at asking follow-up questions to help me develop a better understanding of the material.
- I really appreciated the learning assistant reviews. They were really helpful in studying before an exam.
- LAs really helped clarify concepts and explain topics very well.
- They provided sounding boards for curiosity and frustrations.
- LAs are easy to approach and very knowledgeable about the material, so they are a great resource for students in the classroom.
- Learning Assistants (LAs) were generally helpful in guiding us through weekly worksheets, and from these exercises, I was able to improve my understanding of the material.
- The LA-led review sessions were helpful.
- It was good to have another perspective.
- The LA review sessions are pivotal to my learning and summing up everything prior to an exam.
- The LAs helped with learning strategies and review sessions were awesome.
- It was good to have an extra person to answer my questions.
- Much of what LAs do could be accomplished by TAs or required the assistance of TAs.
- My LA helped to clarify confusing topics and was very knowledgeable when teaching us during discussion.
- They really helped make the material applicable to real life.
- The review sessions they hold are helpful.
- LA's were good for additional tips on studying and ways to approach topics.
- It's helpful to have someone that recently took the class explain how to do well in the course
- PS111B wouldn't be the same without LAs!!
- Having an LA in section allowed us to get more advice and hear different ways of understanding topics.
- They were helpful in explaining discussion worksheets.

Post-Course Survey Open-Ended Question Responses on Learning Assistants (contd.)

- They created very helpful review sessions prior to exams.
- Having LAs in addition to TAs to help teach and foster learning is so helpful. Marisa brings a different perspective, which is helpful because she provide examples of how to study/learn topics.
- It was very helpful to have another person to approach with questions!!
- LAs enhanced the experience via additional supplementation and different explanations on various topics.
- The LA was amazing at introducing new ways to memorize or understand concepts so it was easier for us to pick up during discussion! In addition, the LA review sessions were super helpful extra reviews for me on what's important to study!
- They helped simplify concepts to make it easier to understand.
- I think that the participation of LA's during discussion is somewhat limited; TA's tend to simply answer all of the questions & LA's just go over 1 or 2 questions.
- It's helpful listening to their learning tips as well as just having them go over material again so it can sink in better.
- LAs were most helpful by their hosting of Exam review sessions.
- They are really helpful in discussions, and their review sessions before exams are really helpful.
- My LAs have been a helpful extension in reviewing and solidifying the material.
- I don't really utilize them. get the most out of studying by myself.
- They really help with providing their perspective of the content and solidify our knowledge.
- They often explain things in a way where we can understand the concepts better.
- LA's were helpful in going over questions and helping out the TA. It was another person in the room with experience in the material that was able to help out.
- The LAs were THE BEST. Their review sessions are always really well constructed and useful and their help is always appreciated during discussion. Couldn't imagine the course without them.
- They had a lot of knowledge about material.
- They help reach more students during disc. & often have their own tips for learning the concepts.
- I honestly can't imagine this class without LAs! With professors changing so often during the core series, it has been so crucial to have a home base consisting of TAs and LAs. I really appreciate all the time and effort they spend in discussion and during LA review sessions. They've also helped me feel more comfortable within the PhySci major in general!
- The LAs often-led practice questions during discussion and also helped answer questions. Marisa always provided good analogies to help remember the information which was helpful.
- Learning assistants helped me better connect to the teaching staff and the material and served as a bridge between TA and student as well as professor and student.
- Throughout my experience as a PhySci major, LAs like John and Marissa helped me develop my skill set and have encouraged me not to give up and given me methods to tackle hard content!
- The learning assistants were always able to clarify confusing parts of questions or concepts and guide my thinking when I was challenged by questions during discussion.
- They help foster another point of view to allow students to learn. Sometimes their explanations can make more sense than others.
- Other than going over some of the discussion worksheets, they seem to try to fill the same space as the TAs only with less power.
- Yes, LAs are always so helpful in discussion and during the review sessions. Even when I thought I already knew the answer, I always learn more after talking to them.
- They helped solicit a good learning environment with people ready to ask questions.
- It's really important to have an additional resource to work with during the section because it would be really difficult for the TA to handle all questions and group discussions alone. Also, their review sessions really help me organize the broad topics of the module to identify where I should focus my last bit of studying.

Post-Course Survey Open-Ended Question Responses on Learning Assistants (contd.)

- They help to guide us through the thought process behind discussion questions and to deepen our understanding of the material by asking us why we think something. In addition, they are also really helpful at explaining concepts and answering questions about various topics. Their review sessions are very comprehensive and helpful as well.
- All the LAs were immensely valuable resources for my questions about how to do well in the class, more information on solving a problem, and material covered in lecture. They're very knowledgeable on how to understand the root concept and how to apply it to questions which is something we didn't get a lot of practice in later modules.
- All the LAs were immensely valuable resources for my questions about how to do well in the class, more information on solving a problem, and material covered in lecture. They're very knowledgeable on how to understand the root concept and how to apply it to questions which is something we didn't get a lot of practice in later modules.
- LAs helped guide group discussions and helped us think in the right direction. They also made sure to break down practice problems into simpler questions and then put everything together, which really helped me when I had to work on things individually.
- LAs just helped answer questions during discussion that TAs could do as well.
- Marisa is the best at explaining things, she is knowledgeable but at the same time she challenges us to get it on our own. I like having LAs there because they are easier to talk to than Professors or even TAs at times (love the PhySci TAs though) so they are an integral part of my classes
- I think they are very helpful in discussions and it's beneficial to have another person we can ask questions to if you have had recent experience in the course.
- They were very helpful and helped take some of the question-and-answer work from the TA.
- They provide more coverage than just the TA
- The LAs were so important! I really appreciated their detailed review sessions and their input during discussions.
- They helped break down the info to be more digestible; also really appreciated their review sessions!
- Super helpful in asking to follow up questions, getting us to think more
- TAs have been extremely helpful in my learning as a PhySci student!! Being able to have students who can answer questions while the TA is teaching is very helpful!
- They present a different perspective on the material different from the professors and TAs.
- I LOVE THE LAs WE NEEDED THEM. The LA review sessions were so helpful and I feel like their knowledge balanced well with the TAs.
- Learning assistants help personalize the learning experience in PhySci by interacting with students in a closer setting. It makes big classes seem smaller and more personal
- They made the material easier to learn because they gave us study tips on how they learned it. They also made tackling the material less intimidating.
- Learning Assistants were always there to answer a question when the TA was helping someone out. It was easier to understand a topic when someone who was in my shoes can explain it to me.
- I see their benefits to the class in general, particularly people who are struggling to understand the material or have more questions. I didn't benefit specifically from them being in the course, but I do think they're helpful.
- LAs are super great for learning. They are very approachable and sometimes have different knowledge from the TAs in how they learned in these courses before.
- I found the LA-led questions during the discussion section to be very helpful in understanding the content taught. These questions and the explanations the LAs gave were helpful for my studying later on for the quizzes and tests for each module.
- LA's learned the content recently and are able to give us tips on how to remember concepts just as they used for the class.

Post-Course Survey Open-Ended Question Responses on Learning Assistants (contd.)

- They give students another source to reach out to if students are confused about certain topics. They are also slightly more approachable than a TA or professor because they have just taken the course and know how to study for it and know what to expect. Furthermore, it is really helpful to have them go around and ask if people understand each concept.
- LAs can bend down to our level easily considering the fact that they are undergrad students too and have been through the same cycle not so long ago.
- I think LAs have always been an integral part of the learning experience in my years in undergrad. There are never enough instructors for students, and having even just the slightest bit more of extra help is appreciated in propelling us forward.
- My LAs were really helpful, especially in 107 and 111B. Weirdly, I felt that they were less helpful in my experience taking 111B, particularly for the fact that we had discussion in a lecture hall (CS76) rather than the original, small discussion room we were assigned to. Nonetheless, LAs were very approachable and helpful, especially when answering worksheet questions.
- I think they were helpful but found I learned more from their help in 107 or 111a.
- I find the LAs helpful in 111B because they took the class very recently, so they remember what it's like to take this class and teach us strategies they used when they took the class last year.
- Learning Assistants are especially valuable because they have recently gone through the course and can provide excellent advice.
- Learning Assistants stimulated helpful discussions in sections which help to learn the application questions better.
- I felt as if the learning assistant integration in this course was kind of useless, the TAs could have easily done their job, which seemed to me to be to go over the discussion worksheet questions and try to explain why. Normally, the TA would help explain too, or the LA would be confused.
- Our LAs did absolutely nothing in our discussion sections. I think it slowed us down more having LAs than actually helping us.
- Learning assistants are great for guiding the discussion and explaining difficult concepts.
- I found it helpful that they helped us solve problems and think critically.
- LAs helped greatly in understanding concepts from lectures that were not easily grasped the first time around.
- LA's were very helpful in explaining the class questions but I wish they were more involved in our learning like they were in 107.
- LA's really helped guide me and understand why my reasoning is correct or incorrect.
- Learning assistants asked questions and asked us to explain our reasoning, which helped further my understanding of the material and think more critically.
- They were very supportive.
- It's been awesome having more perspectives on how to approach these classes! Plus, they are so amazing and cool!

Post-Course Survey Open-Ended Question Responses on Benefits and Drawbacks of Learning Assistants

- It is great to have a student there who has taken the class recently.
- The benefits include being able to approach them since they have taken the class only a year prior. The drawback is that they might not be able to answer all students' questions.
- The benefits are that they are another outlet for help and resources.
- They provide extra perspectives and another avenue of learning if there is a disconnect with the professor or TA.
- Benefits: I'm comfortable asking them questions, they know what students commonly get confused with, they set up helpful review sessions. Drawbacks: they can't always answer questions in depth like TAs can, so we don't always utilize their help.
- One minor drawback is that there isn't enough time for all students to interact with the LA at least once during the discussions, but the main benefits are that LAs help teach the content and allow us to practice.
- The LA's are another resource to us and the more resources, the better. The only drawback I can think of is there may be room for confusion if the LA's explain something differently than the instructors.
- They have taken the class before.
- The benefits are having students similar to our and have taken the course recently to empathize. It also is nice for them to break up sections and hear a different voice to keep me engaged. Drawbacks are maybe them not expanding on course material.
- Benefits were talked about above but not really any drawbacks.
- Only benefits because it's another person who can answer your question.
- Benefits: offloads work from TAs
Drawback: at times, LAs do not know course material
- They have recently taken the classes and have such helpful feedback from recent quarters.
- LAs are always available for support, and since they've taken the course recently, they are very knowledgeable about the topics we're studying.
- The benefits are having someone who can relate who very recently took the course.
- I don't see any drawbacks; I just see benefits as some of them took the course recently and can give advice on how professors test.
- The benefit is that the LA's provide their very helpful review sessions.
- I can't think of any drawbacks.
- There are no drawbacks. They are so helpful in explaining complex topics.
- There are no drawbacks. It allows seniors to be involved and give advice to those following them. It provides a more one-on-one experience in sections.
- Benefits = more people to ask for help in section
Drawbacks = sometimes make things more confusing
- The major benefit is extra help in discussion. There are no drawbacks.
- I think it is very important to have LAs in this PhySci department core series. They are able to teach us the material in a way that is beneficial for the exams.
- Benefits: Having someone who has recent experience being a student in the class.
No drawbacks
- Benefits: having a peer that is knowledgeable in the material to help us learn, be a resource in how to study, and reword explanations to make it make more sense
- The benefits are tremendous with the extra support and there are no drawbacks!
- LA integration only contains perks, for example, the LA review sessions and detailed slide deck and practice questions they offer.
- Only benefits, a second way of explaining everything

Post-Course Survey Open-Ended Question Responses on Benefits and Drawbacks of Learning Assistants (continued)

- Benefits were having young people who understand us and have been through what we have to explain to us. Drawbacks were nothing!
- Benefits are extra help and support, but sometimes TAs can grow reliant on LAs.
- I think that the participation of LA's during discussion is somewhat limited; TA's tend to simply answer all of the questions & LA's just go over 1 or 2 questions. The largest benefit would be the LA review sessions, which are very helpful.
- It's beneficial to have students who have experienced this themselves to share their experience and other tips they have. I don't see any drawbacks from a student standpoint.
- I would see no drawbacks of LAs in 111B. There are many benefits including the hosting of the exam review sessions.
- Benefits: provide their views/strategies
Drawbacks: none
- They simplify concepts that are difficult to grasp and clarify things.
- A benefit is having review sessions.
- No drawbacks, but definitely it was nice to have more people available to help us with content we found confusing!
- The benefit is that we get to learn from peers and we have more people to go to for help. The drawbacks I feel like might be that the LAs don't always have a huge part in discussions in 111B or A, but they were super useful for 107.
- Benefits: an added level of social and academic support
Drawbacks: I can't think of any
- Benefits: extra people to ask for help, they often have good tips on how to remember information
Drawbacks: aren't really any
- Drawbacks include the fact that sometimes they are under informed/underprepared, and can create misconceptions about the material because their understanding is limited. Benefits include that they help us engage in our learning and participate more.
- There are absolutely no drawbacks! LAs help students learn and give insightful advice and provide additional resources for learning!
- The learning assistants were always able to clarify confusing parts of questions or concepts and guide my thinking when I was challenged by questions during discussion. There have been no drawbacks to having learning assistants.
- No drawbacks, they are always helpful. Benefits include: more forms of help in class, another perspective of the material.
- benefits are having another knowledgeable person in the classroom but the drawbacks are that they aren't really necessary especially in a small class space.
- There are no drawbacks! Having LAs is so beneficial for 1-on-1 support and getting to answer everyone's questions in discussion. They are also sometimes more approachable for us.
- Sometimes confusion might not be cleared up or it can.
- I don't see any drawbacks to having learning assistant support, but the benefits have been having a fellow to ask questions if the TA is intimidating or unavailable.
- Benefits: Help deepen students' understanding of the material and encourage collaboration; help make the class feel more collaborative and like a community
- Benefits include experience on how to do well in the class and rephrasing concepts in class. LAs are also helpful in larger classes where the TA may be busy with other groups. I haven't seen any drawbacks — all the LAs I've had in 111B and the entire 107 and 111 series are very knowledgeable and helpful.

Post-Course Survey Open-Ended Question Responses on Benefits and Drawbacks of Learning Assistants (continued)

- The benefit is that they might explain things differently than the TAs, so sometimes I learn more from them. Also, they make review sessions which I find very helpful. A setback is that it can get confusing when a TA is explaining something and then an LA tries to jump in and help, but I think that can be solved by communicating when the TA is going to talk vs when it's the LA's turn.
- LAs help increase engagement but we do not have group work anyway.
- I think that a benefit is that they seem more approachable than the professors and TAs, having taken this course more recently. A drawback is that sometimes the questions took up too much time when no one wanted to answer.
- Benefits are more people are in correct discussion, more approachable resources, and helping to hammer down concepts.
- They are helpful to ask questions too. I don't think there are any drawbacks.
- The benefits are having extra support. The only drawback would be sometimes they're not as in the loop as the professors and TAs.
- Questions answered more quickly but discontinuation of thought during presentations.
- Honestly there were no drawbacks because the LAs were all so knowledgeable and helpful. They really went above and beyond to supply us with extra review and help to understand topics and practice questions during discussion.
- No drawbacks really; benefits are that it allows for more perspectives on the material/material worded in different ways which helps me to better understand the material.
- I love them and have thoroughly enjoyed their work. The LA review sessions have been super helpful before midterms/finals.
- You get more personal time with them so they can help answer questions! There are no drawbacks.
- They are extremely knowledgeable and help present the information with a different perspective.
- benefits: more approachable, more familiar with content since they just took the Core
drawbacks: I can't think of any.
- There are no drawbacks to having LAs. The benefits include asking questions more comfortably and learning things from a student perspective.
- The benefits are that they are less scary to approach than TAs. They also recently took the course so they give helpful tips.
- They make mistakes in explaining concepts but on RARE occasions.
- There are more people that can be approached, and they are the most like students, so students probably feel most comfortable coming to them. I don't see any drawbacks to having them.
- Benefit: really helpful for the students. approachable. friendly. knowledgeable and often funny.
Cons: I wonder how much more work it is on the LAs to put things together to help us.
- The benefits of having LA support in this course was the clear explanations and reworked examples given by students who had taken the class more recently. A slight drawback of this was that I tended to rely on LA explanations when studying.
- The benefits are they can help us overcome struggles they had while taking the class and get to pass down their study strategies. A drawback might be some differences in content in which they might've had different professors.
- The benefits of having the learning assistant support are that students are able to have another knowledgeable source to contact and ask questions. Furthermore, LAs are able to get to know the students more closely and allow the students to have more one on one interaction if they need it.
- I see no drawbacks. Benefits include having genuine extra help. Our LAs are awesome!
- For 111B specifically, I do wish the LAs could somehow be integrated more, maybe in the review components, rather than guiding us through just the worksheet questions. Half the time they have

to spend standing/sitting as the TA runs through most of the stuff. The 107 course, I think, is a standard to strive for in both the 111A and 111B courses.

- LAs had similar experiences to us so they can give specific advice to how to navigate the major and the courses. Drawbacks are that information can be inconsistent between LAs and their knowledge is limited.
- I think drawbacks are that sometimes it takes longer for the discussion sessions but benefits are that they are able to provide a student perspective.
- I like the explanations but it can take up time.
- The benefit of learning assistants is that they can help students feel more comfortable to ask questions about content. A drawback is that the LAs do not teach as much in discussion sections compared to the TAs.
- Only benefits - they are extremely smart and always willing to provide help
- Benefits: having another person besides the TA to help explain concepts is pretty nice. Can sometimes be less intimidating to talk to compared to a TA.
Cons: None!
- Benefits: having a peer/someone close in age helps with learning, and being able to be more comfortable asking questions to the learning assistant as well.
Drawbacks: none
- LAs took the course more recently so they can try and give study tips/advice, but other than that I feel like in 111B there is no need for LAs.
- Helped clarify questions.
- Benefit: Having a larger support system
Drawback: Sometimes it seems some LA's are easier to understand than others
- It allows for more in-depth discussion and assistance in learning topics.
- The benefits are that there is more group discussion and engagement. There are no drawbacks!
- Benefits: helpful, approachable. Drawbacks: lots of people in one room
- There is a Lot of assistance but it is challenging if other commitments overlap with events such as the review sessions.
- They are always very helpful for guiding the students' learning in discussion.
- I think having them available is very helpful and should be kept throughout the year.
- The benefits are that the LAs can help students understand why certain problems require the solutions they have instead of just telling them what the answers are.
- I don't really see any drawbacks to having LA support in 111B, I just wish there was more of it. I think it's really helpful when fellow students explain the concepts to you in digestible ways.
- LAs really help break down the concepts and understand them in simple format.
- No drawbacks, only an extra person to help out with the learning experience.
- There are no drawbacks, LAs are amazing.
- No drawbacks that I can think of! They are amazing!! I appreciate when LA's don't force us to participate and just allow us to take it all in!
- Benefit- another person less intimidating than the TA to ask questions.
- I'm glad LAs get the opportunity to gain experience teaching, and I like seeing a face closer to my age. The drawbacks were that often the class would be more eager to respond to the TA than the LA, so when it came time for the LA to present their portion most students were unwilling, and it slowed down our ability to get through everything significantly.
- Have access to them during discussion but not readily outside of discussion. Maybe LA could have an office hour.
- The benefit is if they are good they are able to help us understand the content better. But if they suck at teaching then it just fails to have any benefits.
- Benefits are that they are people who have gone through this before and thus have a unique take and experience that is valuable to our learning. I do not think that there are any drawbacks.
- Benefits: they're there to help us. No drawbacks. Just neutral

Post-Course Survey Open-Ended Question Responses on Benefits and Drawbacks of Learning Assistants (continued)

- It's nice to get advice from students who have taken the same course before. No drawbacks!
- Having learning assistants around in the classroom is great because it gives you a more relevant perspective from someone who took the class just a year ago. However, for my sections, Amanda was able to fulfill that need better than the LA's. She was a learning assistant for these classes just a year ago, and she also took them two years ago. Amanda is a fantastic TA!
- It's more useful in 107 where there are more parts that need to be taught and that TA's need more help with. In the 111 series, the discussions involve the TA's lecturing most of the time.
- Benefit: LAs help communicate/translate information
Drawback: LAs are not necessarily consistent across discussions.
- There are no drawbacks! They are very helpful.
- Benefits: extra help and way to learn from a different perspective
Drawbacks: none
- The benefit is having another knowledgeable individual to help.
- It gives an extra perspective and explanation on different topics.
- No drawbacks, but lots of benefits especially if one didn't understand the topic.
- Benefits: more help and resources
Drawbacks: I can't think of any
- I don't think there are any drawbacks!
- I only see benefits of LA support since they help explain concepts in a way students can understand, and they have prior knowledge of the course that can help guide students through the course.
- Benefits: You can comfortably ask questions and ask for advice.
Drawback: It's almost like we're learning the material at the same time or trying to relearn it so asking questions can sometimes be hard if you believe the LA doesn't know or is unable to answer.
- There are no drawbacks as they are here to help students.
- LAs help us understand the course content but they need to do more in 111B.
- They provide detailed feedback on discussion worksheets.
- If LAs were freer to walk around (depending on the classroom used), they're a great way to ask small questions without disturbing the rest of the class. I did not have this experience this time around since our classroom was pretty cramped. Drawbacks are a decrease in efficiency during the LA part of the presentation, since for some reason people seem to want to participate less, at least from what I saw during my discussion.
- An LA can provide a different way of explaining the lecture material.
- No drawbacks, helps to have someone who took the class and knows what info to study.
- LAs are peer figures that can explain concepts in a relatable way.
- I see no drawbacks but the positives are that they are easier to approach and often can relate to what we are going through as well.
- One benefit is that learning assistants helped break down the lecture material to a more understandable concept.
- They're definitely a benefit since it's very easy to talk to them.
- Sometimes there isn't much for them to do, but when there is they do really well and are able to help us learn the material.
- They are helpful in discussions and in the LA led review session.
- I think one of the biggest benefits of having LAs is simply having an extra resource to answer questions! Since LAs are undergraduates as well.
- They also function as a unique support system that helps us feel more comfortable in class.

- The benefits include having someone understand what I am going through as well as explaining concepts in ways that are easy to understand and follow.
- I firmly believe that there are no drawbacks to having LAs in this course. I also find that LAs are beneficial in highlighting key topics and providing an additional source of assistance and perspectives.
- Benefits: extra person to ask questions, shares their own strategy as students who took the courses in the past.
- LAs provide resources like review sessions.
- The benefit is that they've taken the class and understand everything that is needed for the class. The drawback is that they are expected to know everything so that can be time consuming.
- I think that learning assistants facilitate more student-student connections.
- Benefits were definitely the study sessions!!! And the practice questions they constructed for us to test our knowledge. Setbacks were that they weren't so approachable during discussion sections.
- LAs are helpful for review sessions and to interact more with peers in the PhySci major. The only drawback is that since they are students and not TAs, they might accidentally give incorrect information or not know as much about the topics.
- LAs really shined in the review sessions we had before exams but I did not find them to be extremely helpful in the discussion section but that could also be because discussion was very packed with information. LAs are helpful in giving helpful tips and tricks to remember information and concepts.
- I'd rather ask a TA for help, sometimes I'm afraid they don't have all the info, but good for more simple things
- The benefits are that you get to connect with other students in the major, and I don't believe there are major drawbacks
- I think having them help us answer questions during the discussion sections is definitely a good thing. But their role is very limited in the class.
- It makes me more comfortable to ask someone who is closer to my age and grade.
- The worksheets sometimes feel pretty forced in that a lot of times we don't get to it, so either using fewer questions or incorporating it more seamlessly would improve this. Otherwise it is going well.
- Benefits are that they provide an important learning resource. One drawback is not being readily available. This is something that can't really be addressed without compensating the student for their time outside of section.
- Benefits: They are very approachable because they are near our age, they show how interesting the class can be, they understand what we are going through because they recently took the class I don't think there are any significant drawbacks.
- LAs offer another way of learning the material/another person who explains concepts slightly differently.
- They asked us questions about material that felt helpful. It is nice having an undergraduate student who has taken the class recently to help.
- Benefits: LAs are very relatable!
Drawbacks: LAs might not be as knowledgeable

Post-Course Survey Open-Ended Question Responses on Problem-Based Learning Worksheets

Question: Did you find Problem Based Learning Worksheets integral to your learning in PS 111B?

- The worksheets helped a little but I wouldn't say they were integral
- Since they were modeled after the exam, the study questions were helpful in understanding how the questions would be asked on the exam.
- The discussion worksheets think critically about the topic and allowed me to apply the concepts we learned in class.
- They are a good way to test knowledge before exams.
- Worksheets were great in helping me confirm what I know and what I still need to study.
- The worksheets provided good practice that helped me test my understanding of the weekly material.
- They were helpful in checking where I was during the modules.
- The worksheets were applicable to real life scenarios and helpful to prepare for tests.
- The discussion worksheets were ways for me to practice applying different concepts and preparing for the exams.
- I thought it was a waste of time and would rather have had that time to continue with the TAs explaining concepts.
- I was able to find the topics I didn't understand well yet when I attempted to apply them in a problem.
- They asked good application-based questions.
- The questions were very thought provoking.
- The worksheet questions do not always relate to the course material.
- Yes! Helps you understand the concept more and simulate class questions.
- It helps apply material to real life applications, and makes us think about test-like questions in a low stress environment.
- It helps solidify the material for me to be able to practice the material and see it applied in practice.
- Worksheets were a good review and recap of the current week's material.
- Yes they are great examples of ways to test our knowledge before the quizzes and exams come around and we can study from them.
- It was helpful to show practice problems that are similar to exams.
- They ask for more understanding & are good learning checkpoints.
- Practice is always good to let us apply what we learn, and gain a better understanding of the material.
- They provided practice problems for the content, which provided a lot of help as practice questions for lecture material can be hard to make.
- They were helpful, but I would not say they were the most important resource, or even one I looked back to for exams.
- It helped me simulate the exams.
- I would do just as well in the class if I didn't do them. I just need myself and the material to do well.
- They help me to apply the concepts.
- Worksheet questions gave us insight into what could be tested on.
- Yes I can't imagine the course without them. They help me pinpoint what I'm lacking in and also give me a chance to talk to classmates and create a social environment which is something that I've really missed during covid lol

Post-Course Survey Open-Ended Question Responses on Problem-Based Learning Worksheets (continued)

- Applying concepts is so necessary to prepare for exams.
- Walking through a way to approach problems together on the worksheets helped.
- It was great to have real world applications!
- The practice questions provided a good way to apply the information we were learning even if they didn't look like the exam questions. They are a good study tool.
- I think they didn't really do much and were more like busy work for the class. Not to mention that they took up a lot of class time. I think discussing answers was the most beneficial part of the worksheets because it allowed us to share ideas.
- The questions helped me assess what kinds of questions I should be able to answer for exams!
- They were extremely helpful in helping me understand concepts in a full circle.
- The topics covered in the discussion section did not come up on exams since the two are written by different groups of people. While it is helpful to solidify some concepts from the course, it wasn't very integral to me doing well in this class.
- They help me to really see if I can apply concepts on my own.
- I found myself coming to class only looking to complete it and not necessarily as a tool to learn.
- They really help me apply my knowledge and reflect on the most important parts of the lectures.
- They helped test my understanding of the material in different ways and helped me to see the importance of what we study and how it is applicable to real life and clinical settings. In addition, they were super interesting!
- While part of our exams are knowledge-based, a large portion is also problem-solving based and so getting that experience of diagnosing case studies or using equations etc. is very helpful in preparing for exams.
- I think they allow me to think about real life scenarios and a lot of times I find myself searching for more information regarding a topic covered in class. It increases my curiosity and also challenges me to learn something and be able to explain it to someone else.
- It was just questions on the discussion slides.
- I enjoyed the worksheets as they made me think outside of the lecture slide material and apply the concepts to real life. It also helped that the worksheets somewhat resembled the exam questions.
- Oftentimes problems on these sheets correlate directly with material on the exam so they were good practice questions and good for critical thinking.
- They allowed us to test our knowledge.
- The questions helped me think of how the topic could be manipulated by numerous factors, rather than simply regurgitation of the normal conditions we learned.
- I wouldn't say the worksheets were an integral part of my learning, it kind of just served as checkpoints throughout the section.
- They help us think more critically instead of just using memorization.
- Although the worksheets were hard, they challenged my thinking and helped me learn better.
- Questions helped me apply what I am learning and critically think as well as prepare me for assessments.
- Sometimes we would have to complete questions on our own, which was a little less helpful because if I didn't know something, I wouldn't have anyone to talk to or learn from.
- Discussion worksheets are a helpful way to reinforce concepts we cover in class.
- They helped me understand how to apply the material that we were going over. It was nice to see how it expanded.
- There were questions that required me to critically think and apply concepts learned in class to real world situations.
- They provided the chance to think critically about the material as opposed to just listening to a second person lecture about it twice per week.

Post-Course Survey Open-Ended Question Responses on Problem-Based Learning Worksheets (continued)

- The discussion worksheets were kind of short considering we spent most of the time doing content review which was already super helpful. I thought the discussion worksheets didn't really relate to my knowledge in the class. I think the problems we do during lectures can already be helpful enough.
- Doing the application-based questions and case studies in this class, especially in the first two modules, was integral in helping me apply the concepts and making sure I understood the most important details taught.
- They help us understand what type of questions we might be asked and what material we should know how to apply.
- Having extra practice problems in class was really helpful in letting me learn how to apply the concepts to actual problems. By doing that, I can also understand concepts better.
- They encourage us to think about material through application.
- I think this is more of a “maybe” answer for me. Sometimes I wonder if doing the worksheet ahead of time might be more helpful, because sometimes we'll go over the concept the question is asking about, and then immediately do the questions. This kind of feels like just regurgitating information, but being able to do that is important, too? So yeah, kind of on the fence about the worksheets.
- Worksheet questions were great to test whether I could apply my knowledge to a real-world scenario. They also were similar to case studies, for example, so they were helpful in applying the knowledge to a research setting as well.
- The questions are essential for critical thinking and for preparation for the tests themselves but I thought those were good to have during discussion and that the worksheets were too much especially at the beginning of the quarter.

Post-Course Survey Open-Ended Question Responses on Problem-Based Learning Worksheets (continued)

- The discussion worksheets were helpful because they were often a scenario or case study, which required students to critically think about the question and think about many different topics to answer the question.
- The problem-based learning discussion worksheets allowed me to think as a physiologist/scientist which is how I will need to think when I become a doctor, so it was definitely very useful for me.
- They helped me understand the concepts and how they could be used in an application setting.
- The discussion questions are great for testing what we know so far.
- Super helpful and good way to test understanding.
- More practice questions and develop strategies while studying.
- They helped me study better in terms of solving problems rather than just reviewing the notes.
- I enjoyed the worksheets because they were usually indicative of some of the concepts on exams.
- They weren't that similar to the exam questions but they helped me think about and apply the material that we learned.
- The worksheet format helped apply concepts to real life scenarios and helped me think critically
- Expanded on material learned in class
- It's been cool seeing example problems that are relevant! Just to be sure that I'm approaching problems with a valid mindset!
- Studying the different mechanisms is easier when looked at through the lens of various diseases.

Post-Course Survey Open-Ended Question Responses on Problem-Based Learning Worksheets (continued)

- These worksheets were great at allowing students to be walked through a problem similar to the caliber (hopefully) of exam questions. It forced students to think more critically but with assistance, so we got to learn how to think.
- Helped to understand the level of understanding of the material.
- They are good for giving example problems of what to see on the test.
- Some questions weren't reflective of what we needed to know, but ensured that we understood the concepts we were learning.
- Problem based discussion worksheets help us prepare better for the exams.
- It helped use the information we had just been taught.
- It gave me a better idea of what the questions were going to be like.
- They were helpful to see what would be on the exam.
- They help us use our foundational knowledge and apply them to better help us understand.
- They help give us ideas of test format.
- It helped me solidify what I learned in class.
- Good practice and helped me make sure that I understood concepts.
- It wasn't as helpful since they weren't really helpful with the tests.
- They helped us apply lecture material to test-like questions and real-world application.
- It was nice to have practice questions, but it would be nice to have access to these worksheets after completing them in the same week.
- The discussion worksheets allowed us to practice the critical thinking we need to take our test and also allowed us to better understand the topic we learned that week.
- The discussion worksheets provided an overview on the physiology of the kidneys.
- The worksheets were very helpful!
- They were good indicators of exam style problems.
- They were helpful but not integral.
- Often the discussion worksheets were helpful in preparing for the exam and helped me solidify what to study.
- Problem based learning discussion worksheets helped make the course material understandable.
- They help us develop critical thinking skills and apply the lecture content.
- I felt sometimes they were too specific or too long, I would rather my TA lecture during discussion.
- I found that they were overall helpful in helping us think critically about the material!
- It helped me to learn how to apply multiple concepts to solve a problem.
- Honestly the worksheets seemed like busy work that just had to be done and the topics covered in the worksheets didn't seem especially essential.
- Problem-based questions allowed me to apply the concepts I learned in class and understand better the pathophysiology of diseases.
- Doing problems helps to demonstrate understanding by applying.
- They helped give us some ideas about how to think about problems.
- I thought that the problems on the discussion worksheets helped to improve my understanding by making me think more deeply.
- They were really good check-up questions to important content from the week's lectures. I really enjoyed them.
- I think they helped solidify my knowledge better. Made me feel more confident.
- This was very useful for practicing for exams and interacting more with the material instead of learning it passively.
- The questions were extremely helpful in checking if I was able to understand the concepts well and synthesize a good understanding of them to a level where I could solve a new problem.
- I love applying my knowledge and not having to listen to someone talking forever.

- Yes, problem-based learning is one of the reasons why physiology is interesting as a topic. Applying the concepts that we have learned helps to solidify the importance of them and add layers of complexity.
- I think the worksheets are a great way to learn during the course. Although maybe using these assigning these worksheets before the section as a pre-test could help us by giving us more time to ponder over the questions and be more effective learners.
- They provided good applications to course content.
- It helped me find what I do and don't understand.
- The discussion worksheets that made us apply the info we learned to real-life scenarios made me more interested in the content.
- They helped propose challenging questions on lecture content, forced us to engage in lecture content during discussion
- The discussion questions helped me to think more about the material in different ways.

Post-Course Survey Open-Ended Question Responses on Benefits and Drawbacks of Problem-Based Learning Worksheets

- Benefits: test knowledge actively
Drawbacks: none
- The benefit is the application of lecture material. The drawback is that it cuts into discussion time.
- Benefits are they are a good way to test knowledge. The drawbacks are that there are only a couple questions and may not represent the exam.
- Benefits: great way to apply new concepts Drawbacks: sometimes difficult/stressful to get through when material is still new.
- One benefit of using problem-based learning is that we get to see how well we understand the material while also practicing for exams. One drawback might be that some questions on the worksheets were too simple, and they could have been more like the types of essay questions we saw on exams.
- I can't think of any drawbacks, they're great in applying our learning.
- The benefits are that we get to make our errors in discussion and work together to process our reasoning to questions. This helps to understand how people process and approach problems differently. The only deficit is that sometimes people answer quicker than you can think.
- It is hard if concepts are confusing and haven't been grasped.
- They helped me get more oriented to the topics we were learning and prepare for exams.
- The drawback is that sometimes I attempt a problem before I have studied the content and it's not the best use of my time.
- Some of the questions were not completely relevant or accurately difficult in relation to what the professors expected us to learn. Helps delicious critical thinking.
- Seems like busy work sometimes that is not always beneficial to our learning.
- Benefits: practicing with material in questions
Drawbacks: maybe not enough studying done in order to answer these questions
- The benefits are being able to practice the material; the drawbacks are temptation to compromise actually understanding the material with just trying to get the right answer and not understanding the process.
- Benefits are they are great examples of ways to test our knowledge before the quizzes and exams come around and we can study from them. No drawbacks.
- Benefits are that it allows practice for exams.
- Benefits- good practice; drawbacks - more grading and work for TAs
- Benefits: Keeps students engaged
Drawback: None

Post-Course Survey Open-Ended Question Responses on Benefits and Drawbacks of Problem-Based Learning Worksheets (continued)

- Pros- help for exam prep and thinking about the material in a larger way than just reading off lecture slides
Cons- only useful when you have had time to learn the material before discussions (i.e. have had time to watch the lectures)
- The benefits: simulation
Drawbacks: lack of student engagement in the conversation.
- Forced people to think about the information but if someone is behind then they don't get much out of it.
- They help me prepare for the exams. Sometimes we don't get through all of them.
- No drawbacks, good for mock exam questions
- Benefits: extra practice. Drawbacks: we don't always finish in class
- Got practice with exam-style questions but did take away time from learning content
- Benefits: develop critical thinking and application skills
No drawbacks
- Benefits: allows us to apply the information we are learning in lectures
Drawbacks: sometimes they take too much time or we don't get to finish all of them during discussion section
- Drawbacks include the fact that they took valuable time out of discussion. For example, if I was behind on the material, the worksheets wouldn't do anything at all. I think establishing an understanding of the problem helps me learn better than actually solving it. Sometimes we went over the problem and answered way too quickly and it literally did nothing for me. Benefits include the fact that the questions were used as discussion points for sharing of ideas in groups, which helped me understand things better.
- Sometimes they would cut into learning time but overall they were extremely helpful!
- If you aren't caught up in the material, you will be completely lost.
- The drawback is if the question is not representative of the test questions. The benefits are that it keeps new info we learned refreshed in our minds. It also allows us to work with others.
- Whether you know the material or not is what defines whether you can complete the worksheet for its intended use.
- Drawbacks are that we sometimes don't get to everything, so they add another deadline to think about outside of class time. Benefits are thinking more actively about the topics instead of just listening to lectures. I would be way more likely to zone out if we didn't have occasional breaks to do practice problems.
- I haven't encountered any drawbacks — I feel more well prepared and confident in my skills when doing problem-based worksheets and studying! I better understand the concepts and how to apply the knowledge we learn in lecture.
- I think the benefits are that we get problems similar to the ones in exams. One setback is that it can be frustrating when I don't know the answers.
- I think they could help apply the information but were too simple to really help.
- A benefit is what I mentioned above: applying the concepts outside of class material. A drawback is that problem-based learning makes us focus on only those specific example problems and no other possible problems.
- I think there is so much material to cover that having time to work on questions and then presenting answers slows down time. I think questions should be made easier (like in the second half of 111B) and there should be one or two after every slide and a big group discussion to make sure everyone got it. It would be briefer discussions but all material would get covered.
- I think they are beneficial for using the information we learned but sometimes we don't have enough time to do them in discussion and I think they would be more helpful during live lectures.

Post-Course Survey Open-Ended Question Responses on Benefits and Drawbacks of Problem-Based Learning Worksheets (continued)

- Sometimes the problem-based learning questions were niche or depended on relatively obscure background knowledge to answer the question.
- Good for applying knowledge
- The drawbacks are that difficult questions can stress me out sometimes... but it's up to me to continue studying and use them to feel more confident.
- Benefits: increase learning and memory retention
Drawbacks: not enough time to finish them
- They help expand the course material beyond what is talked about in lectures.
- Benefits: lecture is so fast paced that discussion is great for reviewing and solidifying what happened
Drawback: just not enough time!
- The only drawback of this system is when the difficulty of discussion questions don't match the difficulty of the course content.
- Benefits are that they help apply the material that we know. The drawbacks are that they take some time from covering other material.
- These allow you to see how physiology plays out in real world situations but can sometimes be overwhelming if the question requires a complex answer.
- They only provide benefits, which is to apply the material in a class where outside resources are not very accessible.
- The benefits of this learning style was that it helped me interact with the content more and think deeper into the mechanisms behind what we were taught. One downside was that this learning style often took longer than normal discussion styles, and we sometimes ran out of time to cover content during discussion.
- A benefit is that if we get the question wrong, we might be more motivated to learn and understand why. A drawback might be that some students lose motivation when they don't know how to approach certain problems.
- Benefits: More understanding of the material. An idea of application questions on the exam.
No drawbacks!
- Benefit is that they are a good test of whether I can put what I've learned in class together.
Drawback is that I sometimes had to answer them without having watched the lecture, so I wasn't sure how to answer them.
- I think the questions themselves were integral and necessary but in discussion I was more often than not more worried about submitting the worksheet than actually learning what was being asked so I think they should be kept in discussion but I felt the worksheet was a bit much to keep up with given the time crunch.
- The benefit is that it makes students use higher-level thinking to answer the questions. The drawback is that the questions could be more difficult to understand.
- I think it's very beneficial. It shows how much you know.
- The benefit of having problem-based learning is that it prepares PhySci students to think like scientists, which is what they will need to be doing in their future careers. It also allows PhySci students to gain valuable experience. A drawback of problem-based learning is that some exam questions that were problem solving were challenging to answer, and it made me guess for some of them.
- I like it more than questions that don't require much thought and test your learning, and don't see any drawbacks to it.
- It took a lot of time to get through.
- There are no drawbacks for the worksheet. The benefits are that we get to test our knowledge over content.

Post-Course Survey Open-Ended Question Responses on Benefits and Drawbacks of Problem-Based Learning Worksheets (continued)

- They don't reflect tests all that well.
- Problem based learning allows for the application of the knowledge in a clinical way instead of just memorizing and regurgitating the information.
- I don't see any drawbacks for this either but it would be helpful if they were more similar to the way of thinking reflected in the exam questions.
- Benefits are that they develop critical thinking and true understanding and retention if the material. Drawbacks are that they can be frustrating and cause anxiety when we don't know how to answer them.
- They were good for discussion. However in lecture sometimes professors lectured in addition to the pre lecture material, and presented very few questions or problems to work on.
- Sometimes it's hard to comprehend the questions, and it's awkward when we're made to solve problems in a group when we all don't want to take a go at it
- Benefit- allow you to think more complexly about topics in the class Drawbacks- if you are lost, you kind of have to wait until we go over the answer to ask questions.
- Worksheets kept me engaged with the material and helped make sure I understood material to a slightly deeper level. The only drawback is if you forget to submit the worksheet you can't make up those points.
- Benefit is it gives us examples of what to expect for the tests. Drawbacks is that sometimes some of the questions are not well made for the scope of the class
- They are definitely helpful because they provide us an opportunity to think critically rather than simply regurgitate information.
- The benefits are that it teaches you to think critically about the information most of the time. There aren't really any drawbacks that I can think of
- I think it was helpful for us to learn about how to approach the problems.
- They help us not just memorize but learn the content and be able to apply it outside of class
- Benefit: Helps us think critically
Drawback: They can be a bit complex or too open-ended at times.
- Drawbacks, time spent on them was a lot, didn't help with exams
Benefits, allowed you to think deeper
- I think that sometimes more instructional learning is helpful.
- There are only benefits of problem-based learning since they allow for more practice questions to prepare for the exam.
- There are no drawbacks and it helps us understand the topics better.
- They are sometimes too long, and we don't have enough time to finish during discussion.
- The benefits include an increase in critical thinking, examples of problems that help students think differently and in a way that will prepare them for the exam.
- No drawbacks, benefits helped me focus my energy on key topics.
- The benefits are learning how to answer more complex questions and the drawbacks are sometimes the questions are more complex than what we are expected to know.
- One benefit is that the LAs help better explain the problem-based worksheets.
- One benefit would be that it does help strengthen our knowledge.
- Benefits are that discussion gets students thinking and involved.
- Benefits: examples of clinical problems, drawbacks: take up discussion time that ta could lecture
- I think the benefits of using problem-based learning in sections is that it not only allows us to engage critically with the material, but also gives us a chance to engage with our peers.
- Benefits include teaching me how to apply the concepts learned to a problem. It helps me to study.
- I don't think there are any drawbacks to using problem-based learning but I don't think these worksheets are the best way.

Post-Course Survey Open-Ended Question Responses on Benefits and Drawbacks of Problem-Based Learning Worksheets (continued)

- Benefits: apply concepts learned in class
Drawback: can be difficult
- It is one way to demonstrate learning but sometimes they are not reflective of exam material
- The benefits are that they help give us types of problems that might resemble what exams are like. But the drawbacks are that they can still be confusing and not even applicable to exams if they aren't even covered, and they can be boring and too long for one question.
- I don't think there are any drawbacks. It's pretty interesting to learn about certain case studies/experiments and concentrated questions to reflect our understanding and knowledge over the week's content.
- It was a lot of repeated information that would be redundant. It helped guide me into understanding what were the most important concepts to understand.
- This type of learning is beneficial for testing to see how much we understand and interact with the material on a deeper level. It can be a drawback in that we have too much information to review and problems to solve in class. So then we rush through the material and don't get to spend enough time talking through the questions.
- I think it is VERY useful and NECESSARY to check understanding with problem-based learning as the exams do test that. The only drawback might be that it can be difficult to approach such problems if the material is very fresh and in some cases it was very dense so that added to the challenge..
- More interactive; sometimes take away from reviewing concepts with professors when done in class.
- The major benefit is that it makes you apply the concepts you are learning and helps to think about them in a different light. However, sometimes problems can be too detached or be unrealistic because you are ignoring other factors that would usually play a role.
- I think they really help me prepare for the exams but having them done during the discussion section, when we don't have time to think and simply copy what the TAs say doesn't allow time for thinking about answers.
- It can be demoralizing sometimes and make me feel dumb with topics I don't understand. That is more of a personal ego problem. I do find them again to be super resourceful and help as a baseline to what my weaknesses are.
- The benefit is that it makes the class much more interesting, and also pushes us to think in ways we would have to think in the real world, where we have to decide what information is applicable to a complex situation rather than just being asked questions with clear answers. A possible drawback was that we were not sure if the content in these worksheets would be tested, and how much of the background info of the problems we had to know.
- Benefits: exposes us to different ways the material can be learned,
Drawback: unknown if these will be reflected in the midterm
- Benefits-- critical thinking; Drawbacks-- difficult to find an answer if your foundational knowledge on the topic is shaky

Implementation Guide for Instructors

a. Lecture: This course was offered in a hybrid format. Both in-person and the Zoom online platform were utilized for lectures. Lecture slides, video recordings, discussion worksheets, and additional handouts and resources were shared weekly through the course Canvas platform. Lectures were scheduled for three times a week (MWF) using a flipped classroom approach, and each lecture was 1 hour and 50 minutes in length. Faculty typically utilized only the first hour of Monday and Wednesday mornings for class and Fridays were reserved for review sessions prior to a midterm and the administration of the actual midterm. The course was split into 4 modules taught by three faculty members in the IBP department who specialize in endocrinology, cardiology and respiratory physiology, renal, and integrative (metabolism) physiology. Each professor incorporated their own sets of practice questions to complete with students during the lecture and developed their own set of learning objectives for each module (topic) of the course independently. The instructor and TAs mainly facilitated active learning during these sessions. Lecture content was assessed formatively through mini-lecture quizzes that accounted for 25-40% of the total points of each course module. A summary of which specific weeks these quizzes were administered can be found in Table 1.

b. Teaching Assistants and Learning Assistants: A total of 6 TAs assisted with the course with each TA teaching 2 out of the 12 discussion sections. The TAs were graduate students in the Physiological Sciences Master's Program at UCLA and had completed UCLA's undergraduate Physiology course series prior to graduate school. Each TA led a discussion section of approximately 20 students. All LAs were 4th year undergraduate Physiological Sciences students who had previously completed the core major series successfully and were selected by C.M.. There were a total of 12 LAs in course with each LA assisting 1 of the 12 discussions. These LAs received weekly pedagogical training through the Learning Assistant Program at UCLA to help facilitate small group discussion during C/PBL. Both TAs and LAs received discipline-specific guidance from C.M. by going over the worksheet content prior to the discussion sections each week to ensure that key principles were equally highlighted in each discussion. Unlike the TAs, however, the LAs could not grade, get paid, or provide office hours to students. However, LAs received departmental course credit through the Learning Assistant Program.

c. Grading Scheme: Class grades were based on a straight scale. Grades were assigned based on a points system. For each module, points were distributed across multiple, smaller assessments instead of a single exam. Discussion section points were also awarded and broken down based on completion of quizzes, critiques, participation and C/PBL worksheets and surveys. A breakdown of total points and percentage distribution can be seen below.

Course total = 430 points

Four Lecture Modules = 320 points total

- Module 1 = 100 points
- Module 2 = 80 points
- Module 3 = 40 points
- Module 4 = 100 points

Discussion Section = 110 points total

- Graded assignments = 70 pts
- Attendance and Participation = 30 points
- Weekly worksheets = 9 points + 1 point for pre- / post- surveys

d. Discussion Sections: We implemented C/PBL sessions facilitated by learning assistants during the weekly discussion sections which took place on Wednesday, Thursday, and Friday of each week following the lecture content. All discussion sections were synchronous and held in person. Attendance was mandatory and the discussion sections were 1 hour and 50 minutes long. The first 30 minutes of the discussion were allocated to the TA who reviewed the high-yield principles that were

taught in the lectures. Students then focused on completing C/PBL worksheets in an active learning environment facilitated by the TA and the accompanying LA. The discussion-led activities were interactive and connected the course content with real-life applications. During the discussion sections, students were provided with a C/PBL worksheet that consisted of a list of learning objectives and a set of short-answer questions. The questions were prepared by C.M. and several former undergraduate students based on the principles of Bloom's Taxonomy²⁵ and were scaffolded in order of increasing difficulty (see Sample Discussion Worksheet in the Supplemental Information). These worksheets covered topics that were addressed from the week to actively engage students in the material they were learning (See Table 1). Questions asked students to recall simple facts, to scenario-based questions of different processes related to lecture concepts, and finally challenged students to analyze a piece of data from a primary literature paper or a clinical case study. Discussions surrounding these questions were initiated by the TA and LA intermittently throughout the duration of the section. At the end of small group discussions, LAs would lead the class review of the questions under the supervision of the TA. The discussion-led activities were intended to be interactive and were utilized to connect the course content with real-life applications.

At the end of the discussion worksheet, students completed a series of short questions to assess students' attitudes about the topic for that week and about their interactions with their learning assistants. Students submitted the completed worksheet onto Canvas the same day and were awarded points for participation. Each worksheet was worth 1 point for a total of 9 points for the quarter. A pre-course and post-course survey of the discussion section was also completed during the first and last weeks of the quarter and students were credited a total of 1 point for completing the surveys. A summary of the 10-week course can be found under Table 1.

- e. **Midterm and Final:** In lieu of a traditional midterm and final, students were administered a total of 4 non-cumulative exams throughout the duration of the quarter (Table 1). Each exam covered a specific module and accounted for 60-75% of the points attributed to each module. Exams were administered in-person during lecture.
- f. **Homework Assignments:** Students either turned in a written critique or completed a quiz on primary literature articles relevant to the topics discussed in the lecture. During even weeks, students completed asynchronous quizzes due prior to the first discussion section of the week. Typical quiz questions focused on the methodology of the experiments and the relevance of the assigned research article in relation to the lecture material. The purpose of these quizzes was to assess students' ability to apply lecture knowledge to real-time scientific data. During odd weeks, students submitted a 1-page critique on the assigned primary literature paper prior to the first discussion section of the week. Students were expected to first summarize the article discussing the purpose, general methods, results, and basic conclusions. In the latter half, students were asked to analyze the article and its value and to propose potential future research directives. The purpose of these critiques was to assess students' ability to write scientifically and be comfortable with analyzing primarily research literature and its relevance to physiological principles. Homework assignments accounted for 25-40% of the points attributed to each module. A complete summary of when quizzes and critiques were administered can be found in Table 1.